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Comparative Analysis of Leadership Style and Job Performance among University Librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated on comparative analysis of leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study had a total population of 151 librarians. Total enumeration sampling technique was employed to include all the university librarians. Data was collected using an adapted questionnaire. The instrument was validated by three experts in the field of library and information science. The instrument was trial-tested for reliability on 50 librarians from the institution that did not form part of the study. The scores obtained from the trial-testing was calculated using Cronbach Alpha method and the coefficient of the alpha was 0.78. Data collected was analysed based on frequency count, percentage, mean and standard deviation and multiple regression analysis was conducted to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that the job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria was moderate following the norm test of mean ($\bar{x}=63.7$). The types of leadership styles practised in university libraries in Oyo state, Nigeria are; democratic, charismatic, autocratic and bureaucratic. There was a weak and negative relationship between leadership style and job performance among librarians ($r = -.037$; $p < 0.05$). The study concluded that leadership style is an important determinant of job performance among university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria. The study also recommended full participation of university librarians during accreditation exercise of university courses among others.

Keyword: Job performance, leadership style and university librarians

Introduction

University library is the fulcrum of educational activities, hence, provides support for teaching, learning, research and any sort of academic activities. To achieve these, library collects, processes, organises, stores, preserves, disseminates and evaluates information sources in various formats which include printed and non-printed. The university library facilitates the collecting, organising, storing, dissemination, and assessment of information for effective decision-making, institutional development, and economical progress. The university library plays a very essential role in supporting the mandate of their institution's research, teaching as well as community service by critically selecting, possessing, processing, keeping and giving out relevant information resources within and beyond their environments (Unegbu, Babalola and Basahuwa, 2020). The need for a library in an academic institution cannot be overemphasized because they help in fulfilling the purpose of aiding the curriculum and research in the university. Emphasising the importance of a university library, Eruvwe and Omekwu (2020) noted that university library offers services to the university in the area of learning, reading and advance research. They further noted that academic libraries are known for two major responsibilities which are: to aid and support the school curriculum and to support the research of the university, college as well as that of the students. Academic libraries are the "treasure house" of knowledge which meets the needs of academic, innovators, technocrats, researchers, students and those that falls within the confines of higher education, and this is because they reflect the community they serve.

University librarians have responsibility to help students become information literate (Aharony, Julien and Nadel-Kritz, 2020). They performed the core of the job that actually project the library. Such job includes, acquisition, processing, evaluating and weeding or information resources. It also involves some other specialised services such as: library consortia, selective dissemination of information, library loan, current awareness and any other required services. Arguably, when the information resources are not well consulted it becomes an issue to be worried about and may amount to waste of university resources. This could be as a result of library personnel not developing good collection management skills or the unfavourable work environment factors which may lead to poor job performance. Job performance is a deliberate act of achieving set goals and objectives. Job performance is the measure at which an output is produced as result of the level of inputs given. In the opinion of Hashmi, Ameen and Soroya (2019), job performance provides insights into the human psychology of work

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behaviours and factors that motivates. Job performance which has gained a wide range of definition from various scholars is a determinant of the success or failure of an organisation to a large extent. Job performance is the discharge of statutory duties based on library personnel field of specialization which is centered on the attainment of the library objectives. Personnel experience by the researcher indicated that library personnel have not been meeting the expected level of job performance in the library, especially in this present study locale. Scholars have pointed to the fact that the job performances of library staff in Nigerian universities have not been meeting the set levels of expectation in certain tasks. Reduced efficiency in services of the library, decline in prompt services and the misuse of resources as well as low turnout of research output are evidences of library personnel low level of job performances. This situation, if allowed to persist may impinge negatively on the overall effectiveness of university libraries and academic culture of Nigerian universities. Davidescu, Apostu, Paul and Casuneanu (2020) showed that expectations of job performance on a job are predicted by work-related behaviours of employees and leadership style practiced by the organisation. It is these work-related behaviours and right leadership style that turn into tangible job performances needed to meet the goals and objectives of the library.

Various studies on leadership have been conducted over the years. However, a widely accepted definition is still lacking. According to Talat, Amed and Ali (2015), leadership is a thorough process that outlines delegation of authority, responsibility, and power. For the benefit of the organisation and the individual, leaders support their followers (workers) in accomplishing personal and organisational goals and objectives. According to Kumar (2014), leadership is the act of inspiring others to work toward a common objective and guiding an organisation in a way that improves its cohesion and cohesiveness. Leadership qualities including convictions, ethics, values, morals, personality, knowledge, and talents are used to achieve this. O'Connor (2020) defines leadership as the process by which a person inspires a group of others to collaborate in order to achieve a common objective that is advantageous to both the individual and the group. Utilising effective leadership techniques can inspire and motivate staff members to grow as well as persuade them to give their all for the organisation's success. In his contribution, Ekpenyong (2020) put forth the idea that leadership is the process of inspiring followers to offer everything they have in order to achieve organisational objectives. Leadership is now a team effort between the leader and followers to better the organisation rather than a solitary activity of the leader. Leadership requires the use of persuasion and influence rather than force or coercive dominance. Leadership is a continuous and gradual process with the main objective of helping the organisation achieve a specific goal. According to Adserias, Charleston, and Jackson (2017), leadership is the process of encouraging a group or individual's activities toward achieving goals in a particular situation for the overall benefit of the organisation.

There are different types of leadership style in university libraries and these include; autocratic leadership style, democratic leadership style, laissez faire leadership style, transformational leadership style, transactional leadership style, bureaucratic leadership style and charismatic leadership style. Northouse (2021) asserts that poor or inappropriate leadership philosophies can directly affect employee productivity and retention in today's organisations. Eze, Enwereuzor and Ugwu (2018) contend that a strong leadership style encourages employees to have a connection to the organisation. Those who do so experience a sense of ownership and are more likely to stick with the organisation. Eze, Enwereuzor, and Ugwu (2018) assert that an exceptional leader not only unlocks subordinates' potential for increased productivity but also attends to their needs as they relate to achieving organisational objectives. In their study on understanding the relationship between leadership and organisational performance, Fenwick and Gayle (2008) conclude that, despite the hypothesised leadership-performance association proposed by some academics, present data are inconclusive and difficult to interpret. Organisational justice is promoted through leadership style, which is significant because employees who see organisational fairness have higher levels of work performance, trust in their supervisor, psychological ownership, and organisational commitment. A leader who prioritises work-life balance fosters performance. Work-life balance perks have the ability to increase an employee's quality of life while also increasing company effectiveness (Peters and Heusinkveld, 2010). In their contribution, Sulaiman et al. (2011) argue that leadership style and effectiveness are the key emphasis for organisations in order to achieve organisational goals and generate organisational commitment in their personnel. Sifuna (2012) discovered, on the contrary, that in many African universities, leaders are recruited and awarded based on their academic qualifications, research, teaching, and community service rather than their leadership potential, and that critical training in planning process, budgeting, human resource development, and faculty management is rarely received. Leadership styles, in a nutshell, have a substantial impact on job performance of university library personnel. A university's library leadership style influences its culture, which in turn influences its performance. Klien and Salk (2013) demonstrated this by employing the four-element theory of leadership and data obtained from 2,662 individuals working in 311 firms. The type of leadership style influences corporate culture and job performance. Hence, the current study is to investigate and compare the different leadership styles practiced in university libraries and their effect to job performance of university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria.

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Statement of the Research Problem:

University library is the pivot around which the teaching, learning and research activities of the university revolves, without which no university can attain its goals and objectives. The importance of the library is, therefore, underscored by the huge resources allocated to the library annually. These resources include personnel, space, facilities, equipment and annual budgetary allocation. The personnel of every university library are categorised into three, these are professional (librarian), para-professional and non-professional. The librarians engage in both administrative and technical duties. The administrative duties including making policies, programmes, planning annual budgets, training of other library personnel and coordinating the entire system of university library. While the technical duties are cataloguing and classification of information resources, aligning library programmes with the institution's curriculum, assisting users identifying and retrieving information resources among others. Despite these expectations from the university personnel, literatures and observations have continually shown that users and management of university libraries are generally not satisfied with the job outcome of some library personnel (Northouse, 2021), especially in the area of meeting of deadlines as well as quality and quantity of job performance (Davidescu, Apostu, Paul and Casuneanu, 2020). This state of affair may not be unrelated to the management of the library or in a specific term, leadership style of the library (Eze, Enwereuzor and Ugwu, 2018). Once a wrong leadership style is been practiced in any university library, the result can be low performance, low patronage of users, not meeting up with deadlines, low quality and quantity of productivity and the likes. When these factors are left unchecked, it is capable of affecting the entire library management and the university system from meeting up with its goals and objectives. However, the overall goal of the study is to investigate the comparative analysis of leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Ascertain the level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria;
2. Determine the types of leadership styles practised in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria;
3. Find out the relationship between leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Research Questions:

The following questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria?
2. What are the types of leadership styles practised in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study employed descriptive research survey research method. This research method is a quantitative in nature and aim at collecting data from sample of a given population. The population of the study consists of all professionals (librarians) and para-professionals (library officers) in the eleven university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. The university comprised one federal university, three state-owned universities and seven private universities in the state. A total of one hundred and fifty-one (151) librarians and library officers were sampled for the study. The study adapted the instruments of Modupeola (2018) and Oyewole (2011) on leadership style and job performance respectively. The instruments were adapted because of their similarity in contents while some items were altered because of the variation in the respondents. The questionnaire was subjected to face validation by three (3) experts in the Department of Library and Information Studies, University of Ibadan. The experts vetted the instrument in terms of clarity of expressions, appropriateness of language and relevance to the research questions, and appropriateness of response pattern. They also examined the instrument based on content representativeness. They pointed and removed items considered irrelevant and added other items considered relevant that did not reflect earlier in the instrument. Following their comments, a number of modifications and suggestions were incorporated into the final draft before the questionnaire was administered to the respondents. Frequency count, percentage (%), mean distribution and standard deviation was used to answer research questions. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used to test the null hypotheses.

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Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What is the level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Job performance among university librarians

S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
Contextual performance				
1	I meet up with the approved goals of my section.	2.95	1.11	Agreed
2	I have skill in the use of ICT	2.75	1.11	Agreed
3	My punctuality and regularity to work is satisfactory.	2.25	0.74	Disagreed
4	I collaborate with others to carry out my responsibilities.	2.77	1.02	Agreed
5	My creativity and diligence at work is highly commendable.	2.50	1.03	Agreed
6	I perform work schedules on time.	2.72	1.05	Agreed
7	I have a very good communication skill.	2.30	1.25	Disagreed
8	I always meet the minimum requirements for promotion.	2.54	1.20	Agreed
9	I have coordinating abilities.	2.36	1.26	Disagreed
10	I have the ability to work under little supervision.	2.67	1.24	Agreed
11	My ability to perform competently under pressure is superb.	2.79	1.13	Agreed
12	I promptly attend to request from clients.	2.70	1.13	Agreed
Task performance				
13	I contribute to the overall development of the university.	2.54	1.18	Agreed
14	I contribute immensely to the development of our library.	2.45	1.31	Disagreed
15	I always participate fully on courses accreditations in the university.	2.44	1.26	Disagreed
16	My supervisor loves me for meeting job deadlines.	2.51	1.26	Agreed
17	I have the ability to anticipate problem and develop solution in advance.	2.58	1.15	Agreed
18	I participate in the administrative duties.	2.50	1.25	Agreed
19	I participate in the library routine work daily.	2.52	1.23	Agreed
20	I have received several formal and oral commendations from the organisation and users in the library.	2.73	1.28	Agreed
21	I was once rewarded (eg promotion, price, training and study scholarship) for excelling at work.	2.49	1.18	Disagreed
22	Assessment of quality of work performed.	2.44	1.23	Disagreed
23	Assessment of quantity of work performed.	2.34	1.13	Disagreed
24	I have ability to provide good leadership if given the opportunity.	2.44	0.94	Disagreed
25	My boss loves me for the task accomplished.	2.40	0.95	Disagreed
Overall Mean		63.68		

Source: Field Data, 2024

Test of norm for level of job performance of librarians in the university libraries sampled

Score	Level
0 – 33.3	Low
33.4 - 66.7	Moderate
66.8 – 100	High

From the findings, the overall mean of respondents' level of job performance 63.7 which falls within 33.4 - 66.7. This implies that the level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo State is moderate. Despite the overall moderate level of job performance, there are areas where majority of the respondents indicate low level of job performance. This includes

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punctuality and regularity to work ($\bar{x} = 2.25$); good communication ($\bar{x} = 2.30$); assessment of quantity of work performed ($\bar{x} = 2.34$) among others. The highest performance of majority of the university librarians were based on them meeting up with the approved goals in their respective work section ($\bar{x} = 2.95$) and ability to perform competently under pressure ($\bar{x} = 2.79$).

Research Question Two

What are the types of leadership styles practised in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Types of leadership styles

S/N	Statements	Mean	Std. Dev	Decision
Autocratic leadership style				
1	My supervisor/boss gives me close supervision at work.	3.23	1.03	Agreed
2	Only the leader makes decision in our library.	3.36	0.87	Agreed
3	The UL always takes decision without consulting anyone.	3.33	0.95	Agreed
4	My opinions have never been respected by boss.	3.24	1.02	Agreed
5	Work is more important than human relation to our leader.	2.52	1.11	Agreed
6	My UL have no strong relationship with his subordinate.	3.31	0.84	Agreed
Transactional leadership style				
7	Our boss always rewards workers who excel in their duties and punish those who perform poorly.	1.55	0.94	Disagreed
8	We always work on agreement in my library.	2.60	1.31	Agreed
9	Our leader watches our performance and keeps track of our mistakes.	3.41	0.79	Agreed
Bureaucratic leadership style				
10	My leader is always committed to deadlines.	1.75	1.07	Disagreed
11	My leader asks for commitment via order and rules.	2.49	1.28	Disagreed
12	Our leader treats his subordinate by issuing them order.	3.27	0.89	Agreed
13	We are always assigned to a particular task.	3.48	0.77	Agreed
Laisser-faire leadership style				
14	My UL is not an active supervisor.	2.50	0.96	Agreed
15	My boss avoids work responsibilities.	1.14	0.35	Disagreed
16	UL always leaves decision mandate to subordinates.	3.34	0.89	Agreed
17	My boss is always absent from work.	2.56	0.92	Agreed
18	My boss does not prepare plans for action in the library.	3.21	0.90	Agreed
19	My leader allows his/her subordinate to think and initiate.	3.10	1.01	Agreed
Democratic leadership style				
20	UL always assigns us duties and responsibilities.	3.23	0.99	Agreed
21	Every decision of the library is taken on a round table.	3.40	0.76	Agreed
22	I am directly involved in every decision taken in the library.	3.62	0.76	Agreed
23	My boss encourages the use of uniform procedures.	3.24	0.94	Agreed
24	My leader gives us feedback in work performance.	1.78	1.15	Disagreed
25	UL allocates mandate and authority in random way.	3.09	0.93	Agreed
Charismatic leadership style				
26	My UL takes action before problems escalate.	3.58	0.65	Agreed
27	Our boss decides what is to be done and how it should be done.	2.07	1.30	Disagreed
28	UL always prove his worth as a leader in every discussion.	3.17	0.90	Agreed
29	My boss maintains a definite standard of carrying out task.	3.48	0.88	Agreed
Overall Mean		84.05		

Source: Field Data, 2024

Table 2 showed the results of the types of leadership styles practised in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. The highest of their agreement across the university libraries sampled is that staff are directly involve in every decision taken in the library ($\bar{x} = 3.62$); and that most of the university librarians takes action before problems escalates ($\bar{x} = 3.58$). These two results are one of the characteristics of democratic and charismatic leadership styles respectively. Other common responses were that their bosses maintain a definite standard of carrying out task ($\bar{x} = 3.48$) and that personnel are always assigned to a particular

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task ($\bar{x} = 3.48$). These two responses are common to bureaucratic and autocratic leadership style. It can be deduced from the table that the common leadership styles in university libraries in Oyo state are; democratic, charismatic, bureaucratic and autocratic leadership styles.

Hypothesis 1

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between leadership style and job performance of library personnel in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Relationship between leadership style and job performance

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	r	Sig. (P)	Remarks
Leadership Style	84.05	27.16	151	-.037*	.041	Sig.
Job Performance	63.68	28.62				

Table 3 showed the correlation between leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria. The test was significant with $P < 0.05$. The p-value is 0.041 while the correlation coefficient between leadership style and job performance is -0.37. This shows that there is a weak negative correlation between leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria. In other words, there is a tendency that low or negative job performance among university librarians will affect leadership style(s), and vice versa. The weak correlation also implies that the two variables influence each other at a low rate, hence the null hypothesis is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This sub heading discusses the findings of the study by making interpretations to the responses of the respondents as indicated in the tables above.

Job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria

The level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria is moderate. This implies that university librarians in Oyo State moderately performed their duties. The present moderate level of job performance among university librarians is not farfetched as a considerate number of respondents meet up with the approved goals of their sections, many others have the ability to perform competently under pressure, while some others collaborate with others in carrying out their responsibilities. Also, considerate number of respondents promptly attends to their clients and perform work schedule on time. This is an indication that many of the university librarians will work in accordance to the mandate of the library’s policy to support teaching, learning and research. This findings aligned with the study of Amusa, Iyoro and Ajani (2013) who investigated the librarians’ job performance in public universities in Southwest, Nigeria. Their study revealed moderate job performance with variables such as professional practice, contribution to the overall development of the library, ability to attend swiftly to clients’ request as well as meeting minimum requirements for promotion. The findings of this study is similar to that of Saka and Salman (2014) who investigated the level of job performance of library personnel in universities in North-Central, Nigeria, and revealed a moderate level of job performance of library personnel in universities in North-Central, Nigeria. Their study described the notable barriers of academic librarians’ job performance to include lack of appropriate reward for expanded new roles, lack of status, lack of recognition, social security, social facilities, promotion, wages, social services and physical working conditions. The result of this study is in contrast with the findings of Elvis-Efe and Sahabi (2021), who investigated on the work environment and job performance of librarians in Ahmadu Bello University Library, Zaria Nigeria. Their study revealed high level of job performance of librarians. Also in the contract, Amusa, Iyoro and Olabisi (2013) and Babalola and Nwalo (2013) reported a low job performance of librarians. Babalola and Nwalo investigated job performance as part of the productivity of the librarians in colleges of education in Nigeria. Their study revealed that librarians were less productive in terms of publication output. The reason for the difference between the finding of this study and the existing studies could be

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that job performance of library personnel has improved in the recent times. It could also be as a result of difference in geographical scope of study and the sample areas.

Types of leadership styles practised in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria

The two commonest types of leadership styles being practised in university libraries in Oyo state, Nigeria are democratic leadership and charismatic leadership styles. The study discovered that many leaders in the respective university libraries adopt democratic leadership styles because majority of the respondents indicated that they are involved in decision – making in the library. The fact that some of the leaders allow shared responsibility is also a typical trait of democratic leadership styles. As discovered from the findings, the practised of charismatic leadership style in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria implies that the library heads exhibit sense of mission and personality that can motivate subordinates to execute task given and achieve the set goals. Majority of the university library managers are visionary leaders and have sense of mission. In the same vein, considerable number of the respondents admitted that their heads of departments do not give them feedback after a process or vital decision is taken – a typical autocratic leadership style. Bureaucratic leadership style is also among the types of leadership style common in university libraries in Oyo State, Nigeria. The library heads give priority to the way things should be done based on the laid down principles, policies and procedures. Another reason that pointed to the practised of bureaucratic style in the study area is that, library managers always assign responsibilities to university librarians in the library. It is discovered that the leadership styles that are in practised in university libraries in Oyo State are democratic, charismatic, autocratic and bureaucratic leadership styles. Meanwhile, the study of Olise, Idoko and Ogonwa (2020) corroborate the findings of this present study. Olise, Idoko and Ogonwa equally found that democratic style of leadership is the most prevalent leadership style among libraries in Nigeria. On the same vein, Ukaidi (2016) worked on the influence of three leadership styles namely democratic, autocratic and laissez-faire on the performance of two universities (University of Calabar, River State and University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State) and it was found that democratic leadership style contributed more significantly than the other two which was attributed to its ability in sharing of decision making by both subordinates and leaders in the organisations.

However, this findings is in contrast with the findings of Ukangwa, Onuoha, and Otuza (2020) who found that the most common leadership style among academic libraries in South-east and South-west Nigeria is transformational leadership styles. The variation in the findings of the present study and the existing study may not be farfetched from the fact that each university library adopts leadership styles that best fits their personnel and the working environment.

Leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria

The null hypothesis tested was rejected. In other words, the alternative hypothesis was accepted. Tested hypothesis revealed that there is significant relationship between leadership style and job performance among university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria. This implies that good leadership style has the tendency of increasing job performance of university librarians in Oyo State, Nigeria. Most appropriately, this findings implies that democratic, charismatic, bureaucratic and autocratic leadership style influences job performance among university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria. This result is similar to the findings of Uwandu (2020) who discovered the joint influence of autocratic, democratic and laissez-faire leadership styles on job performance of librarians as significant. This result shows that the three leadership styles have major roles to play in enhancing the job performance of library personnel at every point in time. This study also confirms the result of Chandra (2016) research who tested the influence of leadership styles, work environment and job satisfaction of employees on performance. The results of the regression analysis showed that the leadership style significantly influenced the performance of employees, hence this means that leadership style has an impact on performance of university library personnel.

Conclusion

It can be concluded from the findings that the level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria was moderate. Job performance among university librarians has a significant impact on the service delivery to users. If university librarians discharge their duties efficiently, it will encourage library users to make use of the university library and resources more often and this will help to improve the quality of education in university system. However, the major predictor to job performance among university librarians is leadership style. Practically speaking, the type of leadership style practised by the managers in the university libraries greatly determines the level of job performance among university librarians. Thus, leadership style is an important determinant of job performance among university librarians in Oyo state, Nigeria.

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Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Although the level of job performance among university librarians in Oyo State is moderate, there is still room for improvement. This is because university librarians in Oyo State are still lagging behind in some aspects as regards their job responsibilities. It is worrisome to note that regularity to work of some library staff is questionable. This kind of performance is unacceptable anywhere. Heads of libraries need to first leave by example and then encourage other library staff on the need for regularity at work. This irregularity at work can be controlled by assigning a Quality Control (QC) officer who monitors regularity and punctuality of library staff.
2. There is a need address the partial participation of university librarians during accreditation exercise because it is one of the few areas where the job performance of the staff is low. Library administrators should organise workshops for university librarians to be sensitised on the need for their full participation during accreditation of university courses. Apart from the workshop, the management should ensure that proper communication and follow-up is done when the date of course accreditation exercise is approaching.

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